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Federated Learning for Collaborative Inference Systems: The case of early exit networks[☆]

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ABSTRACT

In today's increasingly diverse computing landscape, end devices like sensors and smartphones are progressively equipped with AI models tailored to their local memory and computational constraints. Local inference reduces communication costs and latency; however, these smaller models typically underperform compared to more sophisticated models deployed on edge servers or in the cloud. Collaborative Inference Systems (CISs) address this performance trade-off by enabling smaller devices to offload part of their inference tasks to more capable devices. These systems often deploy hierarchical models that share numerous parameters, exemplified by deep neural networks that utilize strategies like early exits or ordered dropout. In such instances, Federated Learning (FL) may be employed to jointly train the models within a CIS. Yet, traditional training methods have overlooked the operational dynamics of CISs during inference, particularly the potential high heterogeneity in serving rates across the devices within a given CIS. To address this gap, we propose a novel FL approach that explicitly accounts for variations in serving rates within CISs. Our framework not only offers rigorous theoretical guarantees but also surpasses state-of-the-art training algorithms for CISs, especially in scenarios where end devices handle higher inference request rates and where data availability is uneven across devices.

1. Introduction

Recent advances in embedded and edge computing have enabled the deployment of AI models on a diverse range of devices [1,2]. Despite these advancements, a significant hurdle in this field is resource heterogeneity within real-world networks, where devices – referred to as nodes – often exhibit differing memory and computational capacities. This disparity renders the deployment of the same uniform AI model across all network nodes impractical [3,4]. To address this challenge, Collaborative Inference Systems (CISs) [1,5–9] enable less capable devices to offload portions of their inference tasks to more powerful devices within the network.

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Table 1

Experimental results for a variety of CIS serving rates on the CIFAR10 and CIFAR100 datasets using an equal data partition across the network levels. Serving rate x-y-z denotes the percentage of inference requests served at early exit model 1, 2, and 3, respectively. All reported accuracy values are the mean value over three independent random seeds.

Dataset	Strategy	CIS serving rate setting						
		80-15-5	60-30-10	45-35-20	33-33-33	20-35-45	10-30-60	5-15-80
CIFAR10	Equal weight	49.9 ± 1.2	60.6 ± 0.9	68.9 ± 0.6	74.9 ± 0.2	80.4 ± 0.2	83.8 ± 0.3	85.1 ± 0.4
	FLOPS prop	32.1 ± 3.7	47.3 ± 2.9	58.5 ± 2.3	67.3 ± 1.7	76.4 ± 1.1	83.2 ± 0.7	86.3 ± 0.6
	Serving rate (ours)	54.2 ± 2.4	62.6 ± 1.5	69.2 ± 1.3	74.9 ± 0.2	80.9 ± 0.2	84.6 ± 0.5	86.7 ± 0.5
	Balanced Adj (ours)	53.4 ± 2.2	61.1 ± 1.2	69.2 ± 0.7	74.9 ± 0.3	80.4 ± 0.5	85.0 ± 0.2	87.6 ± 0.5
CIFAR100	Equal weight	39.8 ± 1.2	45.9 ± 0.9	51.0 ± 0.6	55.2 ± 0.3	58.3 ± 0.2	60.3 ± 0.2	61.1 ± 0.3
	FLOPS prop	30.4 ± 0.7	40.0 ± 0.6	48.3 ± 0.4	53.3 ± 0.0	58.0 ± 0.1	60.9 ± 0.1	62.1 ± 0.1
	Serving rate (ours)	45.0 ± 0.7	50.2 ± 0.7	53.0 ± 0.8	55.2 ± 0.3	53.2 ± 1.0	56.2 ± 0.1	57.9 ± 0.5
	Balanced Adj (ours)	46.6 ± 1.2	49.5 ± 0.8	52.1 ± 0.6	54.8 ± 0.3	57.4 ± 0.2	59.3 ± 0.8	60.7 ± 0.2

While most existing research on CISs assumes these AI models are already trained and focuses on either optimizing their placement within networks and/or developing collaborative inference serving policies [1,7,10–12], much less attention has been devoted to how these models should be trained. Yet, the effectiveness of a CIS ultimately depends on the quality of its constituent models and on how well their training reflects the cooperative inference procedure. In particular, existing heuristics typically assign either uniform weights [13,14] or disproportionately large weights to the largest model [15], while neglecting the distribution of inference requests across models. This mismatch can lead to substantial performance degradation when the inference load is skewed. For example, in a representative setting where most requests are served by the smallest early-exit model (e.g., exits after the 5th block of ResNet-18) on CIFAR-100, these methods suffer a severe performance drop – exceeding 15 percentage points in test accuracy – relative to a balanced inference scenario (see Table 1). In this work, we show that the performance losses induced by skewed inference workloads can be avoided by adopting inference-aware training strategies that explicitly account for the cooperative inference procedure. We develop these strategies in a distributed setting where models are collaboratively trained using local datasets available at the same nodes that will later perform inference.

Federated Learning (FL) [4,16,17] provides a framework for such collaborative training, enabling nodes to train machine learning models without sharing their local data. In FL, knowledge transfer among heterogeneous models can be achieved through explicit knowledge distillation – which typically requires a public dataset [18,19] – or by having the models share a subset of parameters. Within this latter approach, the most common method is to jointly train Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) that either share entire layers or specific parameters within a layer. Techniques like Ordered Dropout, which selectively drop parts of the network during training [20,21], and Early Exit Networks (EENs), which allow models to make predictions at intermediate layers [13,22], can be used to customize models according to the varying memory and computational constraints of different nodes.

However, optimizing these shared parameters is challenging because different models may need distinct representations from the same layer to achieve optimal performance. For example, in an early exit network, the layers just before a shallow model’s classifier may prioritize learning features that directly support classification, while those same layers in a deeper model may instead focus on extracting more general feature representations. A crucial consideration in this optimization process for CISs is the role each model plays during inference. Models handling a higher volume of inference requests should exert greater influence on the learning of shared parameters. This ensures that the most frequently requested models are better optimized, thereby enhancing overall inference performance. Despite its importance, previous research has largely overlooked this unique challenge within CISs. Existing training methods, particularly those designed for distributed early exit networks [13,14,23,24], treat all models equally, failing to account for the heterogeneity in model capacities and performance. Only a few studies have empirically suggested assigning weights based on model complexity [15,25], but they still disregard the corresponding inference request rates. Crucially, the existing studies lack theoretical guarantees on inference performance. To bridge this gap, our paper introduces a theoretically grounded FL training algorithm specifically designed to improve overall CIS inference performance.

Contributions.

1. We formalize the first *inference-aware* FL framework for CISs, with the goal of maximizing overall inference accuracy. We define our objective function as a weighted sum of the expected losses for each model, where the weights, Λ , correspond to the expected future inference request rates.
2. We propose a novel and practical inference-aware FL training algorithm designed for CISs. Our algorithm minimizes the weighted sum of empirical losses across nodes, using input weights $\tilde{\Lambda}$ that may differ from the expected rates Λ . Moreover, it enables computationally stronger nodes to assist weaker ones in model training, according to predefined sampling probabilities p .
3. We present the first theoretical analysis of FL for models with shared parameters for CIS. We rigorously analyze the impact of the key parameters $\tilde{\Lambda}$ and p on the generalization error, optimization error, and bias error, providing a deep understanding of how these factors affect the overall training process and final inference performance. From this theoretical analysis, we derive practical configuration guidelines for our proposed training algorithm.
4. We evaluate the effectiveness of our algorithm, showing that it significantly outperforms state-of-the-art methods, particularly in realistic scenarios where end devices handle higher inference request rates.

Outline of paper. This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the necessary background for comprehending CISs, FL, and EENs. Section 3 formalizes the CIS problem, introduces our collaborative training algorithm along with its theoretical convergence analysis, and proposes practical configuration guidelines derived from our analysis. Section 4 offers empirical validation of our claims using standard benchmarks. Section 5 discusses possible adjustments to our training algorithm to address potential malicious attacks and fairness issues. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Background and related work

In this section, we discuss the relevant background necessary to understand CISs, FL, and EENs.

2.1. Collaborative inference systems

Collaborative Inference Systems (CISs) [1,8], also known in the literature as Inference Delivery Networks [7], enable smaller devices to offload part of their inference tasks to more capable devices, and represent an active field of study. The scope of collaboration in these systems may vary, extending beyond the traditional device-cloud model, to include intermediate nodes such as edge servers, regional clouds, or a collective of devices within direct transmission range of each other [1,7,10,11,13]. Collaboration within a CIS can also take various forms, ranging from selectively forwarding complex inputs to more powerful models [7], to splitting computation tasks across nearby nodes [26,27], or combining inferences from similar models in an ensemble approach [28,29]. In this paper, we focus on a hierarchical structure of nodes, each equipped with increasingly complex models that collaborate by forwarding locally computed intermediate representations to more powerful nodes within the network. Although much previous work has focused on optimizing the deployment and utilization of already trained models in a CIS [7,10–12], our research shifts focus to the less-explored challenge of *training* these models in an FL context.

2.2. Federated learning for a CIS

Traditional FL algorithms (e.g., FedAvg [16], FedProx [30]) assume that the participating nodes have similar storage and computational capacities and adopt the same model architecture. Federated distillation techniques [18] rely on a powerful orchestrator to distill knowledge across models with different architectures, but they require access to a public dataset. Some works synthesize the required “public” dataset via federated generative models or server-side synthesis from client ensemble [31,32]. Yet generative models can memorize and leak private data, and differential-privacy defenses degrade utility [33,34]. Federated ensembling techniques [35] independently train an ensemble of lightweight base models across all nodes. However, the architecture of each base model must conform to the computational limits of the least capable node, which can significantly limit the overall inference accuracy of the ensemble. An alternative approach involves jointly training models that share a subset of parameters, offering a more practical solution. For instance, Horvath et al. [21] introduce FjORD, a framework that uses ordered dropout to prune a DNN by channels, creating nested submodels of different sizes suitable for heterogeneous nodes. A similar idea is explored in HeteroFL [20]. Alternative approaches involve the use of early exit networks [23,36] or a combination of these two methods [24,37]. However, none of these works provides a rigorous convergence analysis of their learning algorithms that quantifies the gap between the performance of the obtained sub-models and that of the optimal ones.

While our algorithm and theoretical analysis apply to both pruning (e.g., ordered dropout) and early exit strategies, we focus on early exit networks for clarity and concreteness. Early exit networks also offer the clearest example of collaborative inference, as weaker nodes forward intermediate representations to more powerful nodes. This contrasts with approaches like FjORD and HeteroFL, where the input itself must be forwarded for inferences in a CIS.

2.3. Early exit networks

Early Exit Networks (EENs), introduced initially as BranchyNets [22], extend DNNs by adding classifiers, or early exits, at intermediate layers. For instance, integrating an early exit into a standard ResNet-34 [38] architecture may involve adding a classifier after the 8th residual block yielding a smaller network within the original ResNet-34 that has the same depth as a ResNet-18.¹ The initial motivation for this design was to enable faster inference with less computational cost, which is especially useful in computationally heavy computer vision and natural language processing tasks [27, Table 4]. Fig. 1(a) details the inference process in standard EENs. A prediction is served at an early exit if its uncertainty – evaluated, for example, through the entropy of the corresponding softmax values – is below a predefined threshold [14,15,22]. Otherwise, the intermediate representation is passed to subsequent exits for further processing.² In a CIS, each node stores the portion of the DNN (i.e., a *subnetwork*) up to a given exit, aligned with its computational/memory capacities [13], as illustrated in Fig. 1(b). If the node is uncertain about the local prediction (e.g., the entropy of the confidence vector is higher than a given threshold), it forwards the intermediate representation to a more powerful node (if any).

¹ Each block contains two convolutional layers. At the early exit, the model has a total of 18 layers, including the initial convolution and the final fully connected layer.

² The results in this paper remain unaffected whether the inputs or the intermediate representations are forwarded.

The typical training procedure of EENs involves minimizing a weighted loss across *all* exits [14,15,22,25,39]:

$$\min_{\mathbf{w} \in \mathcal{W}} \mathbb{E}_{z \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \alpha_e \ell^{(e)}(\mathbf{w}, z) \right], \tag{1}$$

where each data sample $z = (x, y)$ is drawn from the data distribution \mathcal{D} , with x as the input features and y the corresponding target. Here, $\mathbf{w} \in \mathcal{W} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ represents the EEN parameters, $\mathcal{E} = \{1, \dots, E\}$ denotes the set of early exits where $e \in \mathcal{E}$ corresponds to the e th exit encountered during the inference forward pass, $\ell^{(e)}$ is the loss at the e th exit, and $\alpha_e \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is the weight assigned to e th exit’s loss. The weight coefficients $\{\alpha_e\}_{e \in \mathcal{E}}$ are crucial in determining each exit’s contribution to the overall model performance and can be assigned in various ways. Traditional training approaches generally assign equal weights to all exits [13,14,23,24,36,40]. We refer to these methods collectively as the “Equal Weight” strategy. Besides, some approaches pick the empirical best weights following the observation that more weights should be assigned to earlier exits [9,22]. Alternatively, more complex approaches have been considered that allocate weights in proportion to each exit’s computational complexity, often measured in FLOPS [15,25,41]. We refer to these methods collectively as the “FLOPS Prop” strategy. We note that all existing approaches are not theoretically grounded and overlook the fact that inference request rates can vary significantly across real-world networks, leading to accuracy drops in likely scenarios where end devices (e.g., smartphones) with shallow models handle most of the requests. Our proposed method addresses this issue by systematically incorporating these varying request rates into the training process.

3. Federated early exit networks for CISs

In this section, we formalize the CIS problem (Section 3.1), present our collaborative training algorithm (Section 3.2), provide theoretical convergence guarantees (Section 3.3), and propose practical analysis-driven configuration rules (Section 3.4).

3.1. Problem formulation

CIS topology. In a CIS, the nodes $\mathcal{N} = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ are often organized in a hierarchical tree structure, where parent nodes possess greater computational resources and memory than their child nodes. This organization is exemplified by the cloud–edge-device scenario [1]. Let $E_i \in \mathcal{E}$ denote the largest exit in the subnetwork stored by node i , and let \mathcal{N}_i^- denote the set of child nodes of node i . We observe that $E_j < E_i, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-$. At *inference*, node i utilizes only its largest exit E_i to ensure the most accurate prediction. However, during *training*, it may be beneficial for node i to also consider earlier exits, as we will illustrate later. The set \mathcal{N}_e denotes nodes that use early exit e for inference, i.e., $\mathcal{N}_e = \{i \in \mathcal{N} \mid E_i = e\}$.

While we adopt this common hierarchical tree topology for presentation purposes, we emphasize that the proposed algorithm (Section 3.2) and its theoretical guarantees (Section 3.3) are broadly applicable to any directed acyclic graph, regardless of the placement of the most powerful nodes within the network.

Real-time inference requests. Local inference requests are generated at each node $i \in \mathcal{N}$ with an *arrival rate* $\lambda_i^a \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$. Node i also needs to process intermediate representations transferred by its children in \mathcal{N}_i^- . The *transfer rate* from node $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-$ is denoted by λ_j^t . Each node i serves locally a fraction $f_i \in [0, 1]$ of the total flow of requests – comprising both local requests and those transferred from its children – using its largest exit E_i . The requests served locally are those with the lowest uncertainty (see Fig. 1 and EENs’ description in Section 2.2), and we denote their distribution by D_i^s . The overall *-serving rate* λ_i^s is:

$$\lambda_i^s \triangleq \left(\lambda_i^a + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} \lambda_j^t \right) f_i, \tag{2}$$

and the corresponding transfer rate λ_i^t :

$$\lambda_i^t \triangleq \left(\lambda_i^a + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} \lambda_j^t \right) (1 - f_i). \tag{3}$$

Fig. 2 presents a straightforward numerical example illustrating how a CIS manages inference requests.

The transfer rate λ_i^t is constrained by an upper limit μ_i^{\max} , determined by the network’s upstream bandwidth or the target inference delays. We assume each node is aware of its maximum transfer rate μ_i^{\max} and an estimate of its local arrival rate λ_i^a . This assumption is realistic, given that in real-world deployments these quantities can be estimated, monitored, or provisioned.

Training objective for CISs. We are the first to formalize the problem of model training in a CIS. Since the primary goal is to minimize the total loss across all served samples throughout the network, thereby maximizing inference quality, it is natural to define the following optimization problem over the model parameters $\mathbf{w} \in \mathcal{W}$ and the serving fractions $\{f_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}_1 : \quad & \min_{\mathbf{w} \in \mathcal{W}, \{f_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \lambda_i^s \mathbb{E}_{z \sim D_i^s} [\ell^{(E_i)}(\mathbf{w}, z)], \\ \text{s.t.}, \quad & \lambda_i^t \leq \mu_i^{\max}, f_i \in [0, 1], \text{ Eqs. (2) and (3)}, \forall i \in \mathcal{N}. \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Building on existing research showing that deeper early exits typically yield higher inference accuracy [11,22,42], we conclude that smaller nodes should offload as many requests as possible to their parent nodes, subject to the constraint $\lambda_i^t \leq \mu_i^{\max}$ for each $i \in \mathcal{N}$.³

³ We illustrate this point by contradiction: suppose in the optimal solution of \mathbb{P}_1 , there exists a node with $f_i^* > 0$ and $\lambda_i^t < \mu_i^{\max}$. By decreasing f_i^* to 0 or to a value that makes $\lambda_i^t = \mu_i^{\max}$ and adjusting f_j^* s.t. a more powerful node j serves these additional requests locally, we achieve another feasible solution to \mathbb{P}_1 with a smaller loss.

Fig. 1. Early exit networks for collaborative inference system.

Fig. 2. Example of a two-level network with four nodes. Each leaf node ($i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$) processes inference requests (λ_i^a) using its local exit (Fig. 1). Requests that meet the uncertainty threshold are served locally (λ_i^s), while the intermediate representations of the remaining requests are transferred to the parent node (λ_i^t). The root node ($i = 4$) serves all incoming requests ($\lambda_4^s = \lambda_4^a + \sum_{j=1}^3 \lambda_j^t$). All rates ($\lambda_i^a, \lambda_i^s, \lambda_i^t$) are given in requests per second (r/s).

This results in the relation $\lambda_i^t = \min \left\{ \mu_i^{\max}, \lambda_i^a + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} \lambda_j^t \right\}$, enabling us to eliminate the decision variables $\{f_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$ and transform the optimization problem \mathbb{P}_1 into the equivalent optimization problem \mathbb{P}_2 :

$$\mathbb{P}_2 : \min_{\mathbf{w} \in \mathcal{W}} \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \Lambda_e \mathbb{E}_{z \sim \mathcal{D}_e} [\ell^{(e)}(\mathbf{w}, z)], \tag{5}$$

where

$$\Lambda_e \triangleq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}_e} \left(\lambda_i^a + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} \lambda_j^t - \lambda_i^t \right) \tag{6}$$

Algorithm 1 Federated Learning for Distributed EENs

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1: Input: a randomized initial model  $\mathbf{w}_1$ , total communication rounds  $T$ , local steps  $J$ , global learning rate  $\eta_s$ , local learning rates  $\{\eta^{(t,j)}\}$  at round  $t$ , and local step  $j$ , sampling matrix  $\mathbf{p}$ , aggregation weights  $\tilde{\Lambda}$ .
2: for  $t = 1$  to  $T$  do
3:   Server samples the set  $\mathcal{N}^{(t)}$  of node/exit pairs w.r.t.  $\mathbf{p}$ .
4:   Server broadcasts model  $\mathbf{w}^{(t)}$  to all nodes in  $\mathcal{N}^{(t)}$ .
5:   for all  $(i, e) \in \mathcal{N}^{(t)}$  in parallel do
6:      $\mathbf{w}_{i,e}^{(t,0)} = \mathbf{w}^{(t)}$ 
7:     for  $j = 0$  to  $J - 1$  do
8:       Node  $i$  selects a random batch  $\mathcal{B}_i$  and updates its local model:
          
$$\mathbf{w}_{i,e}^{(t,j+1)} = \mathbf{w}_{i,e}^{(t,j)} - \eta^{(t,j)} \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}_i|} \sum_{z \in \mathcal{B}_i} \nabla \ell^{(e)}(\mathbf{w}_{i,e}^{(t,j)}, z).$$

9:     end for
10:    Node  $i$  sends  $\mathbf{w}_{i,e}^{(t,J)}$  to the server
11:  end for
12:  The server updates its global model:
          
$$\mathbf{w}^{(t+1)} = \Pi_{\mathcal{W}} \left( \mathbf{w}^{(t)} + \eta_s \sum_{(i,e) \in \mathcal{N}^{(t)}} \frac{\tilde{\Lambda}_e |S_i|}{|S_{e,p}| p_{i,e}} \mathbf{g}_{i,e}^{(t,J)} \right),$$

          where  $\mathbf{g}_{i,e}^{(t,J)} = (\mathbf{w}_{i,e}^{(t,J)} - \mathbf{w}^{(t)})$ .
13: end for
14: return  $\mathbf{w}^{(T)}$ 

```

is the total serving rate of all nodes using exit e at inference time, and \hat{D}_e denotes the data distribution of samples served at early exit e . The serving rates $\{A_e\}_{e \in \mathcal{E}}$ depend only on the arrival rates $\{\lambda_i^a\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$ and the maximum transfer rates $\{\mu_i^{\max}\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$. Before training begins, the cloud can collect this information from all nodes and compute the serving rate A_e for each exit e .

3.2. Federated learning algorithm dissection

We propose an FL algorithm (Alg. 1) that enables network nodes to collaboratively train an EEN for Problem \mathbb{P}_2 using their local datasets. Each node i is designed to hold all exits up to its largest exit E_i . Although node i only uses exit E_i for inference, it can still play a crucial role in training shallower exits, particularly when it owns a substantial amount of data. At each communication round, the server follows a two-step sampling process: first, it samples a set of nodes to participate in training, as in traditional FL algorithms; then, it selects a specific early exit for each chosen node to train. The probability of selecting node i to train a particular early exit e is denoted by $p_{i,e}$, while $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times E}$ denotes the overall probability matrix. The set of nodes with a non-zero probability of training exit e is $C_e \triangleq \{i \in \mathcal{N} \mid p_{i,e} > 0\}$, and the set of all samples from nodes in C_e is $S_{e,p} \triangleq \cup_{i \in C_e} S_i$, where node i holds the dataset S_i .

Our algorithm aims to minimize a proxy of the objective in \mathbb{P}_2 , where the expected loss at each early exit e is replaced by the empirical loss computed on the dataset $S_{e,p}$ and the expected inference request rates A_e may be substituted with a potentially different set of weights $\tilde{\Lambda}_e$. Introducing the weights $\tilde{\Lambda}_e$ is motivated by our theoretical results in Section 3.3. However, even without formal analysis, it is clear that when exit e experiences a high inference request rate A_e but has limited data $|S_{e,p}|$, the empirical loss may become too noisy, making it preferable to set $\tilde{\Lambda}_e \ll A_e$.

The procedure works as follows: At each communication round t , the server samples nodes and their corresponding early exits based on the probability matrix \mathbf{p} (Lines 2–3). The server then broadcasts the current global model to the sampled nodes (Line 4). Each node i performs multiple steps of mini-batch gradient descent on the loss associated with its sampled early exit e , and returns the updated model to the server (Lines 5–11). The server aggregates these updates by computing a weighted sum of the pseudo-gradients, $\mathbf{g}_{i,e}^{(t,J)}$, from each node-exit pair (i, e) (Line 12). Each pair's weight is determined by three key factors: (i) the importance $\tilde{\Lambda}_e$ assigned to exit e ; (ii) the proportion of the dataset that node i used to train relative to the total dataset used to train exit e ($|S_i|/|S_{e,p}|$); and (iii) the inverse of the probability that node i was selected to train exit e ($1/p_{i,e}$).

Practical operation. When client i trains exit e at round t , it updates the model using $\nabla \ell^{(e)}$ (Line 8), while parameters unrelated to the e th loss, such as those for deeper exits, remain unchanged. As a result, these parameters are identical in both $\mathbf{w}_{i,e}^{(t,J)}$ and $\mathbf{w}^{(t)}$, causing the corresponding entries in the pseudo-gradient $\mathbf{g}_{i,e}^{(t,J)}$ to be zero. Consequently, the server does not need to send the entire model $\mathbf{w}^{(t)}$ to all clients. Instead, it only sends the parameters of the subnetwork up to exit e to the clients training that exit, who then return the updated parameters. Before the aggregation step (Line 12), the server zero-pads the pseudo-gradients.

3.3. Theoretical results

Our analytical results assume that the serving distribution of every exit e is the same, i.e., $\hat{D}_e = D, \forall e$. This assumption is automatically satisfied if all local datasets are generated from the same distribution and the nodes' forwarding decisions are

independent of the sample z . However, the typical behavior of EENs, which forward the most difficult requests, introduces an implicit distribution shift. To the best of our knowledge, this shift has not been studied in literature, and we plan to address it in future research.

By taking the expectation with respect to client sampling in the aggregation rule (Alg. 1, Line 12), it becomes evident that our algorithm aims to minimize $F_{S,\tilde{\lambda}}(\mathbf{w}) \triangleq \sum_{e \in E} \tilde{\lambda}_e \sum_{i \in C_e} \frac{|S_i|}{\sum_{i \in C_e} |S_i|} F_{i,e}(\mathbf{w})$, where $F_{i,e}(\mathbf{w})$ denotes the empirical loss at early exit e as computed on node i 's local dataset S_i , i.e., $F_{i,e}(\mathbf{w}) \triangleq \frac{1}{|S_i|} \sum_{z \in S_i} \ell^{(e)}(\mathbf{w}, z)$.

Let $\mathbf{w}^{(T)}$ denote the output of Alg. 1. While $\mathbf{w}^{(T)}$ approximately minimizes $F_{S,\tilde{\lambda}}(\mathbf{w})$, what we are truly interested into is the performance of $\mathbf{w}^{(T)}$ in terms of the expected loss in Eq. (5), which we denote as $F_{D,\Lambda}(\mathbf{w}^{(T)})$. In this section, we provide an upper-bound for the difference between $F_{D,\Lambda}(\mathbf{w}^{(T)})$ and its minimum value $F_{D,\Lambda}^*$. More precisely, we investigate the *true error* of the algorithm:

$$\epsilon_{\text{true}} \triangleq \mathbb{E}_{S, A_{\tilde{\lambda}}} \left[F_{D,\Lambda}(\mathbf{w}^{(T)}) \right] - F_{D,\Lambda}^*, \quad (7)$$

where $A_{\tilde{\lambda}}$ is our algorithm and S is the union of the nodes' datasets drawn from D .

We first list the assumptions needed for our results. Let $\mathbf{w}_{i,e}^*$, $\mathbf{w}_{\tilde{\lambda}}^*$, and \mathbf{w}_D^* be the minimizers of $F_{i,e}$, $F_{S,\tilde{\lambda}}$, and $F_{D,\Lambda}$, respectively.

Assumption 1 (Bounded Loss). The loss function is bounded, i.e., $\forall \mathbf{w} \in \mathcal{W}$ and $z \in \mathcal{Z}$, $\ell(\mathbf{w}, z) \in [0, M]$.

Assumption 2. The hypothesis space $\mathcal{W} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ is convex and compact with diameter $\text{diam}(\mathcal{W})$, and contains the minimizers $\mathbf{w}_{i,e}^*$, $\mathbf{w}_{\tilde{\lambda}}^*$, and \mathbf{w}_D^* in its interior.

Assumption 3. $\{F_{i,e}\}_{(i,e) \in \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{E}}$ are L -smooth: for all \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{w} in \mathcal{W} , $\|\nabla F_{i,e}(\mathbf{v}) - \nabla F_{i,e}(\mathbf{w})\|_2 \leq L \|\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{w}\|_2$.

Assumption 4. $\{F_{i,e}\}_{(i,e) \in \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{E}}$ are μ -strongly convex: for all \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{w} in \mathcal{W} , $F_{i,e}(\mathbf{v}) \geq F_{i,e}(\mathbf{w}) + \langle \nabla F_{i,e}(\mathbf{w}), \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{w} \rangle + \frac{\mu}{2} \|\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{w}\|_2^2$.

Assumption 5. Let B_i be a random batch sampled from the i th node's local data uniformly at random. The variance of stochastic gradients in each node is bounded: $\mathbb{E} \|\nabla F_{i,e}(\mathbf{w}, B_i) - \nabla F_{i,e}(\mathbf{w})\|^2 \leq \sigma_{i,e}^2$ for all \mathbf{w} in \mathcal{W} and $(i, e) \in \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{E}$.

Assumption 1 is standard in statistical learning theory (e.g., [43,44]), while Assumptions 2–5 are standard in the analysis of federated optimization algorithms (e.g., [45–47]).

Theorem 1 provides an upper bound on the true error of our algorithm in terms of the sum of three components: a generalization error, a bias error (due to the mismatch between $F_{D,\tilde{\lambda}}$ and $F_{D,\Lambda}$), and an optimization error. The proofs are provided in Appendix A and Appendix B. We emphasize that our theoretical results apply not only to the early-exit networks considered in Algorithm 1, but also extend to models with shared parameters, such as those based on ordered dropout, as in FjORD and HeteroFL [20,21].

Theorem 1. Under Assumptions 1–5, the true error of the output $\mathbf{w}^{(T)}$ of Alg. 1 with learning rate $\eta^{(t,j)} = \frac{2}{\mu(\gamma+(t-1)J+j+1)}$ and $\gamma \triangleq \max\{8\kappa, J\} - 1$ can be bounded as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{\text{true}} \leq & \underbrace{\mathcal{O} \left(\sum_{e=1}^E \tilde{\lambda}_e \sqrt{\frac{\text{Pdim}(H_e)}{|S_{e,p}|}} \right)}_{\epsilon_{\text{gen}}} + \underbrace{\mathcal{O}(\text{dist}_{\text{TV}}(\tilde{\Lambda}, \Lambda))}_{\epsilon_{\text{bias}}} \\ & + \underbrace{\mathcal{O} \left(\frac{B(\tilde{\Lambda}, \mathbf{p}, \sigma, \{|S_i|\}_{(i,e) \in \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{E}})}{J \times T} \right)}_{\epsilon_{\text{opt}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $\kappa \triangleq \frac{L}{\mu}$, $\text{Pdim}(H_e)$ represents the pseudo-dimension of the class of models for exit e , dist_{TV} is the total variation distance, $\Lambda = (\Lambda_1, \dots, \Lambda_E)$, $\tilde{\Lambda} = (\tilde{\Lambda}_1, \dots, \tilde{\Lambda}_E)$, and the expression of $B(\cdot)$ is provided in Theorem B.2 (Appendix B).

3.4. Configuration rules

Theorem 1 establishes that the aggregation weights $\tilde{\Lambda}$ in Alg. 1 (Line 12) impact all three error components: generalization, optimization, and bias. Furthermore, each component is minimized by a distinct choice of $\tilde{\Lambda}$.

The bias error ϵ_{bias} is dominant when each exit e is trained on a large dataset $S_{e,p}$ (making ϵ_{gen} small) and the number of communication rounds T is high (making ϵ_{opt} small). In such settings, the optimal strategy sets the aggregation weights $\tilde{\Lambda}$ equal to the expected serving rates Λ . We refer to this configuration rule as ‘‘Serving Rate’’, which effectively eliminates the bias error, as $\text{dist}_{\text{TV}}(\tilde{\Lambda}, \Lambda) = 0$. However, optimization and generalization errors can also play a significant role. In such instances, deviating $\tilde{\Lambda}$ from Λ can reduce these errors but at the cost of a non-zero bias error.

Table 2

Results for the 80-15-5 serving rate setting using the highly biased data partition, where the 3 network levels hold 3.4%, 19.9%, and 76.7% of the data, respectively.

Dataset	Strategy	$p = 0$	$p = 0.2$
CIFAR10	Equal weight	36.5 \pm 4.0	–
	Serving rate (ours)	41.3 \pm 2.6	49.2 \pm 2.9
CIFAR100	Equal weight	10.0 \pm 1.4	–
	Serving rate (ours)	17.9 \pm 0.2	30.1 \pm 2.1

The optimization error ϵ_{opt} is strongly influenced by the gradient variance $\sigma_{i,e}^2$ at each early exit e , as shown by the $B(\cdot)$ term in Theorem B.2. Experimentally, we observe that gradient variance is significantly higher for initial exits than for later ones, making the optimization error especially sensitive to the stochastic gradients computed at these early stages (Appendix C). To reduce ϵ_{opt} , earlier exits with higher variance should be assigned lower aggregation weights $\tilde{\Lambda}_e < \Lambda_e$ to lessen their impact during training. In scenarios where the optimization error dominates, it follows that minimizing ϵ_{opt} involves setting the aggregation weights $\tilde{\Lambda}_e$ inversely proportional to the gradient variance $\sigma_{i,e}^2$. We observe that this approach alters the weights in the same direction as the ‘‘FLOPS Prop’’ strategy (described in Section 2.3), which also assigns larger weights to deeper exits.

The generalization error, on the other hand, is affected by the ratio $\text{Pdim}(H_e)/|S_{e,p}|$. In practice, $\text{Pdim}(H_e)$ acts as a proxy for the complexity of the model at exit e . It follows that exits with a larger model (i.e., larger $\text{Pdim}(H_e)$), and smaller dataset (i.e., smaller $|S_{e,p}|$), contribute more to this error component, and thus reducing the aggregation weights associated to these exits minimizes ϵ_{gen} . In extreme cases where the generalization error is dominant, the optimal strategy requires setting aggregation weights to zero for all exits except the one with the lowest complexity ratio $\text{Pdim}(H_e)/|S_{e,p}|$. The probabilities $p_{i,e}$ can also help reduce the generalization error. Indeed, if powerful nodes periodically train exit e , they increase the sample size $S_{e,p}$, leading to a reduced ϵ_{gen} .

In many realistic scenarios, no single error component may dominate, and one might consider configuring our FL algorithm by minimizing the entire bound in Theorem 1. However, this approach is often impractical due to the complexity involved in estimating theoretical parameters, such as the Lipschitz constant L and the strong convexity constant μ . To address this issue, we adopt a hybrid approach that balances reductions in both bias and optimization errors, yielding robust performance across diverse settings. More formally, for a given exit e , we set $\tilde{\Lambda}_e \propto \Lambda_e + 1/\sum_{i \in C_e} \left(\frac{|S_i|}{|S_{e,p}|}\right)^2 \sigma_{i,e}^2$, and we refer to this approach as the ‘‘Balanced Adj’’ strategy.⁴

4. Experiments

4.1. Training details

We consider a ResNet model architecture [38] for experiments on the CIFAR10, CIFAR100, and MNIST datasets, three widely used benchmarks for evaluating both adaptive inference techniques like EENs [15,25,39] and FL algorithms with heterogeneous model architectures [20,21,24].⁵ For CIFAR10 and CIFAR100, we use a ResNet-18 [38] with early exits inserted after the 2nd and 5th residual blocks (CIFAR10) and after the 5th and 7th blocks (CIFAR100), ending with the full ResNet-18 as the final exit. For MNIST, we use a smaller ResNet model with one early exit after the 2nd residual block and a final exit after the 4th block. Unless otherwise noted, each node only trains its latest exit (i.e., $p_{i,E_i} = 1$). We relax this assumption in Tables 2 and E.8 (Appendix E). Additional details about the datasets, training infrastructure, and hyperparameters are provided in Appendix D.

4.2. Evaluation methodology

Baselines. Our work represents the first attempt to develop an FL training algorithm for use within a CIS. Due to the lack of established baselines for direct comparison, we compare our approach to state-of-the-art (SOTA) algorithms proposed to train traditional EENs, focusing on those that lend themselves naturally to extension in FL and CIS settings (see Section 2.3 for a comprehensive description of these methods). The two strategies in this category are: (i) ‘‘Equal Weight’’, which assigns equal weight to all early exits [13,14], and (ii) ‘‘FLOPS Prop’’, which weights the exits according to their FLOPS [15]. While other centralized EEN training methods, such as those proposed by [25,39], could potentially be adapted for our purposes, their extension is less straightforward and would require extra computation by the nodes. Note that these baselines do not provide theoretical guarantees. We also implement the (iii) ‘‘Serving Rate’’ and (iv) ‘‘Balanced Adj’’ strategies, both directly derived from our analysis in Section 3.3. We emphasize that the computational, communication, and memory footprint of our training algorithm (Algorithm 1) is equivalent to that of standard federated learning baselines like FedAvg.

⁴ Appendix C describes the procedure to estimate $\sigma_{i,e}^2$.

⁵ In addition to image datasets, we have also conducted additional experiments on a networking dataset (DTI [48]) for device type identification. The results are presented in Appendix E.1.

CIS topology. We utilize a tree topology as defined in Section 3.1 and considered in related works [1,13], consisting of seven nodes: four in the first level, two in the second, and one in the third, with each level holding a progressively larger subnetwork. Additional experiments and discussion on the topology effect are in Appendix E. In particular, we conducted additional experiments with a larger network consisting of 17 nodes, which confirmed the consistency of our results (Table E.5). Due to computational overhead, this larger network was not used for all experiments. We present results for three data distribution scenarios: (a) an “equal data partition”, where data is evenly distributed across all network levels; (b) a “highly biased data partition”, where data is concentrated on the most powerful devices; and (c) a “biased data partition”, with intermediate skewness.

Serving rates. For our experiments, we model all inference requests as initially arriving at the leaf nodes ($\lambda_i^q = 0, \forall i \in \mathcal{N} : \mathcal{N}_i^- \neq \emptyset$), reflecting a cloud–edge–device scenario in which requests are generated at the device level.⁶ By adjusting the maximum transfer rates $\{\mu_i^{\max}\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}$, we control the fraction of requests served at each exit. Specifically, we define *CIS Serving Rate Settings* x – y – z , where x , y , and z denote the percentage of inference requests served at Exits 1, 2, and 3, respectively. The configuration guarantees that all nodes in C_e receive and serve requests at the same rate. This allows us to evaluate a wide range of serving rates Λ , ranging from most requests being served by end devices (80-15-5) to the majority of requests served by the most powerful nodes (5-15-80).

CIS inference procedure. For the purposes of experimentation, to achieve a given CIS Serving Rate Setting, we use the following procedure for our main experiments:

1. All inference requests arrive simultaneously at the leaf nodes.
2. Each leaf node makes predictions on all its incoming requests, computes the softmax values, and ranks them from most to least confident.
3. The leaf nodes serve their most confident requests, with the number of served requests determined by the percentage specified in the CIS Serving Rate Setting, and forward the remaining requests to the next level.
4. The process continues for nodes on the subsequent level.

Additionally, we also tested the random forwarding strategy where each node randomly forwards the requests to the next level, aligning with our theoretical assumption. The results are shown in Table E.9. We note that simultaneous request arrivals are not required for our theoretical results but are used to simplify experiments. In practice, a threshold can be quickly learned on each node using online quantiles estimation algorithms [49–51], to align with its transfer rate λ_i^t .

4.3. Experimental results

Table 1 presents our results on the CIFAR10 and CIFAR100 datasets under the “equal data partition”. On CIFAR10, our “Serving Rate” and “Balanced Adj” strategies consistently outperform the “Equal Weight” and “FLOPS Prop” methods across all CIS serving rate configurations. The improvement is most notable when the smallest models handle most inference requests, as in the 80-15-5 and 60-30-10 settings, where “Equal Weight” and “FLOPS Prop” perform poorly by failing to account for the actual serving rate distributions. In these cases, “Serving Rate” outperforms “Equal Weight” by 4.3 percentage points (p.p.) and “FLOPS Prop” by 22.1 p.p. in the 80-15-5 setting, and by 2.0 p.p. and 15.3 p.p., respectively, in the 60-30-10 setting. Even when the largest models handle most requests, as in the 10-30-60 and 5-15-80 configurations, “Balanced Adj” surpasses “Equal Weight” by 1.2 p.p. and 2.5 p.p., and “FLOPS Prop” by 1.8 p.p. and 1.3 p.p., respectively. We show in Figure E.3 the training error of every model versus the number of rounds to illustrate the convergence behavior of “Balanced Adj”. In line with model capacity, the device tier stabilizes earlier at a higher loss, the edge tier continues improving throughout training, and the cloud tier reaches the lowest loss with minimal variance.

To better interpret these results, we analyze how different training strategies affect $\bar{\Lambda}$ and, in turn, the CIS test accuracy. First, setting $\bar{\Lambda}$ equal to the serving rate Λ minimizes the bias error ϵ_{bias} , which is the objective of our “Serving Rate” strategy. On the CIFAR10 task, with $T = 100$ communication rounds and a sufficiently large dataset, ϵ_{bias} dominates, allowing “Serving Rate” to empirically minimize this term and perform well across various serving rate settings. In contrast, “Equal Weight” assigns equal weights to all exits, which can significantly increase ϵ_{bias} as serving rates become more uneven, leading to poor performance in scenarios with extreme rate imbalances.

On the CIFAR100 dataset, we observe performance trends similar to CIFAR10 across various device-biased CIS serving rate settings, including 80-15-5, 60-30-10, 45-35-20, and 33-33-33. However, when the largest models serve most requests, the “FLOPS Prop” baseline outperforms our “Serving Rate” strategy, likely due to the greater difficulty of the CIFAR100 task, which results in a larger optimization error ϵ_{opt} . As noted in Section 3.4, strategies like “FLOPS Prop” are expected to perform well in these scenarios. Yet, its performance deteriorates significantly when the inference load shifts to the first-level nodes, leading to an increase in bias error as $\bar{\Lambda}$ diverges from Λ . This results in a notable drop in CIS accuracy, as observed in the 80-15-5 configuration, where “Serving Rate” and “Balanced Adj” outperform “FLOPS Prop” by 14.6 and 16.2 p.p., respectively.

On MNIST (Table E.6, Appendix E), these overall trends remain consistent: “Serving Rate” and “Balanced Adj” show pronounced performance gains when serving rate configurations are uneven, while “FLOPS Prop” works better when inference requests are more evenly distributed across the two network levels.

⁶ Our approach is applicable to any inference request scenario, as the corresponding serving rates can be readily derived using Eq. (6). Each node i measures prediction uncertainty by the magnitude of its highest softmax value. It serves the requests for which it is most confident and forwards the others.

In Table E.7 (Appendix E), we provide results for the “biased data partition” scheme, which has an intermediate level of skewness towards the most powerful nodes. On CIFAR10, “Serving Rate” and “Balanced Adj” again consistently outperform other baselines across all CIS serving rate settings, while on CIFAR100, “Balanced Adj” remains competitive in all scenarios, especially when the first-level nodes handle most inference requests.

Overall, our experiments reinforce the core insights from Section 3.4, highlighting the critical role of error decomposition in selecting aggregation weights $\tilde{\Lambda}$. Our “Serving Rate” strategy, which aligns $\tilde{\Lambda}$ with the serving rates Λ , proves beneficial in scenarios where the bias error ϵ_{bias} is dominant. Meanwhile, our “Balanced Adj” strategy, which incorporates adjustments to account for the optimization error ϵ_{opt} , either leads or closely matches the performance of the best methods across three image datasets, three data partitions, and a wide range of CIS serving rate settings.

Enabling node collaboration through probabilities p . We conduct an ablation study to examine the impact of the hyperparameter p , focusing on extreme scenarios where nodes with the smallest models and datasets serve the majority of inference requests. This scenario is particularly relevant, as end devices typically have limited data storage compared to cloud servers or other more powerful nodes. Results for the most challenging configuration, the 80-15-5 serving rate setting, are presented in Table 2 for both the CIFAR10 and CIFAR100 datasets, where $p_{i,e} = p$ if $e < E_i$ and $p_{i,E_i} = 1 - (E_i - 1)p$. These experiments clearly show that increasing p significantly improves the overall inference accuracy by enabling stronger nodes to support weaker ones during training. Additional results on the impact of p can be found in Table E.8 (Appendix E).

Another extreme scenario may happen that different exits are trained on samples from different classes. For example, large exit (owned by powerful nodes) may lack exposure to certain classes that are primarily observed by weak exit (weak nodes). Our architecture can mitigate this limitation by enabling powerful nodes to delegate inference to smaller exits trained on those specific classes. During inference, a powerful node can select the exit that provides the most confident prediction, rather than relying solely on its largest exit. A deeper investigation of this scenario is left as promising future work.

5. Discussion

5.1. Vulnerability to attacks

Federated learning is known to be vulnerable to adversarial manipulation—including Byzantine behavior, model poisoning, and backdoors [52–55]. In standard FL, a compromised client’s impact typically scales with its aggregation weight. Common practice assigns client i a weight proportional to its dataset size $|S_i|$, which could let a malicious participant inflate its influence by overstating its size. In an actual deployment, the server would cap the declared dataset size for each client and/or audit the number of samples actually processed, preventing any participant from disproportionately increasing its weight. The server would also employ robust aggregation rules to filter out the attackers. For example, geometric-median aggregation [56], coordinate-wise trimmed mean/median [53], and Krum [52] provably tolerate a prescribed Byzantine fraction at the cost of a modest accuracy reduction.

In our setting, an update’s weight depends not only on local data size but also on the exit-level importance $\tilde{\Lambda}_e$ and the sampling probability $p_{i,e}$. Concretely, Algorithm 1 aggregates pseudo-gradients with the factor $\tilde{\Lambda}_e \cdot \frac{|S_i|}{|S_{e,p}|} \cdot \frac{1}{p_{i,e}}$ (Algorithm 1, Line 12). If clients are allowed to declare their inference request rates, an attacker could try to inflate its reported rate to increase Λ_e and, consequently, $\tilde{\Lambda}_e$. A stronger adversary might also misreport its largest supported model to target the exit associated with the largest coefficient $\tilde{\Lambda}_e \cdot \frac{|S_i|}{|S_{e,p}|} \cdot \frac{1}{p_{i,e}}$. Doing so would require detailed system-wide knowledge (topology, arrival rates, transfer limits, and peers’ dataset sizes) to anticipate the server’s choice of $\tilde{\Lambda}$, plus the capability to credibly train the corresponding subnetwork. Even under such assumptions, the attack remains conceptually the same as in standard FL—artificially amplifying a client’s contribution. The countermeasures for both attacks are the same: bound each client’s maximum effect on the update and apply robust aggregation at the server.

5.2. Potential unfairness

One may wonder whether a high heterogeneity in the serving rates across clients could lead to unfairness, with clients handling fewer inference requests experiencing worse inference performance.

First, we note that a low local inference rate at a specific client using model/exit e does not by itself reduce that client’s training importance. In our formulation, the training objective in Problem \mathbb{P}_2 is a weighted sum across exits with weights Λ_e equal to the aggregate serving rates of exit e over the whole CIS (Problem \mathbb{P}_2 , Eq. (5); Λ_e defined via Eq. (6)). If, network-wide, all exits are expected to serve the same number of requests, then the objective gives the same importance to each exit, regardless of any single client’s local request rate. Different exits may still reach different accuracies (they are different-capacity models), which is unavoidable when devices are constrained to different model sizes.

Second, when the aggregate serving rate Λ_e is low because most requests arriving to clients with exit e are forwarded, this is not necessarily harmful for requests arriving at those clients: these queries are served by deeper models at more powerful nodes, typically improving accuracy.

Finally, a genuine fairness risk arises when (i) the aggregate inference rate Λ_e is low and (ii) some clients with exit e cannot forward their requests (e.g., due to bandwidth or latency constraints). We observe that these situations are visible a priori to the orchestrator, since it can compute all local serving rates λ_i^s . There are several mitigations: 1) Impose a minimum value for Λ_e in

Eq. (6) for exits that must serve non-negligible local demand, in order to guarantee a minimum quality level for those models. 2) Adjust model assignment so that such clients train or use a simpler model $e' < e$ with a larger aggregate rate $\Lambda_{e'}$. 3) Adopt a fairness-aware objective by modifying Eq. (5), similarly to what is done in q-FFL [57] or DRFL [58].

6. Conclusion

We present the first inference-aware FL training algorithm for CFSs, demonstrating that inference serving rates impact all components of the generalization error. Our configuration rules, derived from the error decomposition, provide improved accuracy, particularly in scenarios where inference request rates are unevenly distributed across the network. Furthermore, our rigorous theoretical results extend beyond early exit networks, applying broadly to approaches that jointly train models with shared parameters, such as ordered dropout, pruning, and other nested training methodologies.

Our analysis assumes identical serving distributions across exits, which abstracts away the selection bias induced by forwarding “hard” inputs to deeper exits; relaxing this assumption and developing serving-aware generalization bounds under distribution shift is a natural goal for future research. Moreover, our algorithm could be complemented with knowledge distillation—analogously to FjORD [21]. Exploring such KD-augmented variants is another promising direction for future work.

Impact statement

This work has the potential to impact real-world machine learning deployments by improving both the efficiency and privacy of collaborative inference systems. By leveraging federated learning, our approach enables distributed devices to collaboratively train models without sharing raw data, thus enhancing data privacy—a crucial concern in sensitive domains like healthcare and smart infrastructure. Additionally, our algorithm optimizes inference performance across heterogeneous nodes by incorporating dynamic serving rates, which can lead to faster and more reliable AI services on resource-constrained devices. These advancements promote scalable, privacy-preserving AI solutions that empower smaller devices to collaborate effectively with more powerful systems in diverse application areas.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Chuan Xu: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Caelin Kaplan:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Angelo Rodio:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Tareq Si Salem:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Giovanni Neglia:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.peva.2025.102538>.

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Further reading

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